

ADSORPTION STUDY OF Cu AND Pb HEAVY METALS FROM WATER SOLUTION USING $MnFe_2O_4$ AND $MnFe_2O_4$ -Zeolite

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Abstract

$MnFe_2O_4$ and $MnFe_2O_4$ -Zeolite have been synthesized from sand and zeolite using the co-precipitation method for absorbing ions Pb(II) and Cu(II) in aqueous media. Samples were then characterized using SEM-EDX, XRD, VSM, BET, and AAS. The results of SEM-EDX show that the particle shape of $MnFe_2O_4$ and $MnFe_2O_4$ -zeolite is not uniform. $MnFe_2O_4$ particle size is 5-25 μm and $MnFe_2O_4$ -zeolite 2-29 μm and there are impurities such as Mg, Cl, Ti, and V. XRD results confirm the presence of $MnFe_2O_4$ and other phases such as TiO_2 and SiO_2 . VSM measurement shows that both $MnFe_2O_4$ and $MnFe_2O_4$ -Zeolite are soft magnets with coercivity values of 302.12 Oe and 406.04 Oe consecutively. While BET analysis shows that the surface area, pore volume, and pore size of $MnFe_2O_4$ -zeolite are 222.91 m^2/g , 0.30 cm^3/g , and 2.70 nm larger than those of $MnFe_2O_4$. Then AAS measurement shows the optimum adsorption for Pb and Cu ions using $MnFe_2O_4$ at a dose of 100 mg/L are 96.59% and 99.24%, while for the $MnFe_2O_4$ -zeolite adsorbent for Pb ion at a dose of 100 mg/L is 96.91% and Cu ion at dose of 50 mg/L is 99.54%. In general, it was found that the adsorption percentage for both Pb and Cu ions was higher using the $MnFe_2O_4$ -zeolite than the $MnFe_2O_4$.

Keywords: $MnFe_2O_4$, $MnFe_2O_4$ -Zeolite, Adsorption, Co-precipitation, Heavy Metal.

INTRODUCTION

The lead metal ion is considered a long-term pollutant [1] and can cause organ damage even at low concentrations [2]. Not only that, lead and copper are toxic heavy metals. Lead (Pb) can cause severe kidney, liver, and reproductive system dysfunction. Copper (Cu) can cause vomiting, diarrhea, stomach cramps nausea, and even death [3][4]. Given the negative impact caused by waste metal ions Pb and Cu, it is important to purify water to remove contaminants from Pb and Cu ions[5]. Various conventional techniques can be carried out such as reverse osmosis [6], ion exchange [7], chemical precipitation [8], solvent extraction [9], etc. The adsorption method is the most appropriate method for removing heavy metal ions from water, with high effectiveness and economy [10].

Several adsorbents have been used to adsorb heavy metal ions from aqueous solutions; Namely sawdust of eucalyptus, dates, and limes [11], $\alpha - \text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ nanoparticles [12], bentonite[13], zeolite [14], manganese ferrite [15], zinc ferrite [16], manganese ferrite-biochar [17] and bentonite - manganese ferrite [18]. Some of these adsorbents have disadvantages such as low adsorption and difficulty in separating from the solution [19]. With the development of research on advanced materials on water pollution by heavy metals, research on manganese ferrite (MnFe_2O_4) adsorbents continues to grow every year. MnFe_2O_4 adsorbent can be used to remove heavy metal ions with magnetic separation from solution [20]. However, the MnFe_2O_4 adsorbent is easily agglomerated in the liquid phase, reducing the surface area and lowering the adsorption capacity. Zeolite has a larger surface area, more active sites, and high porosity which can increase the adsorption efficiency[21]. Thus, in this Article, the synthesis of MnFe_2O_4 and $\text{MnFe}_2\text{O}_4 - \text{zeolite}$ using the co-precipitation method and their ability to absorb Pb(II) and Cu(II) metal ions from aqueous media will be reported.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

In this study, the synthesis of MnFe_2O_4 and $\text{MnFe}_2\text{O}_4 - \text{zeolite}$ has been done using the co-precipitation method. The coprecipitation method has a simple process and can produce particles that are very small grain size and tend to be more uniform. However, the coprecipitation method will not be able to remove impurities completely. MnCl_2 (98%), iron sand, and clinoptilolite zeolite were used as the main precursors. Iron sand that has passed 200 mesh is dissolved using 17 ml of HCl (37%) and stirred at 500 rpm for 30 minutes at 80°C, then filtered using Whatman filter paper (Grade 40 Circles). The iron sand filtrate was then mixed with MnCl_2 solution with a ratio of 2: 1. Furthermore, stirring was carried out with a magnetic bar at 500 rpm at room temperature until the solution became homogeneous. $\text{MnFe}_2\text{O}_4 - \text{zeolite}$ was made by adding 1 gram of zeolite to the solution followed by stirring for 40 minutes at 500 rpm at room temperature. Next, the temperature of the solution was changed to 70°C before adding sodium hydroxide solution (5 mol/L) to adjust the solution pH value to 11, after which the resulting solution was stirred for 1 hour. The precipitated composite was then dried in an oven at 100°C for 24 hours. The composite was then crushed using a mortar and ready to be used as an adsorbent. The samples were then characterized using X-ray diffraction (XRD smartlab rigaku) and Scanning Electron Microscopes (SEM-EDX Hitachi SU-3500), Brunauer

Emmett-Teller (BET, Micrometrics ASAP 2020, USA), room temperature hysteresis loop measured by Vibrating Sample Magnetometer (VSM 250). In the batch adsorption process using a shaker carried out at optimum conditions (pH=5, T=25°C, t= 60 minutes, $C_i=8\text{mg/L}$)[18], [22] and the results will be tested using Atomic Absorption Spectrometry (AAS Agilent Technologies-200 series AAA/240 FS AA).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Adsorbent Characterization

The surface morphology of MnFe_2O_4 and MnFe_2O_4 – zeolite adsorbents obtained from SEM-EDX measurements are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Surface morphology of adsorbents a) MnFe_2O_4 , and b) MnFe_2O_4 – zeolite, c) Zeolite and Elemental content of adsorbents d) MnFe_2O_4 , e) MnFe_2O_4 – zeolite, and f) Zeolite

Figure 1a shows that the shape of the MnFe_2O_4 particles is not uniform, the surface is still not uniform. The non-uniformity of the particle shape is indicated by the size range of the MnFe_2O_4 adsorbent particles from 3 μm to 25 μm . Particles with a large size (21 μm) experience agglomeration, because natural interactions occur between magnetic particles causing several agglomerated areas [23]. Whereas Figure 1b shows the MnFe_2O_4 – zeolite adsorbent also having a non-uniform particle shape and size. The particle size range of the MnFe_2O_4 – zeolite adsorbents is 2 μm and 29 μm . It seems that on average the particle size of MnFe_2O_4 – zeolite is larger than MnFe_2O_4 .

Figure 1d shows that the MnFe_2O_4 adsorbent has several elements such as O, Na, Mg, Al (0.72%), Si (0.28%), Cl, Ti, V, Mn, and Fe. All these elements are mostly found in all iron sands with different percentages. The highest percentage of elemental content was in the elements O, Fe, and Mn which are 38.13%, 27.71%, and 8.48% consecutively which confirmed the formation of the MnFe_2O_4 compound. Whereas Figure 1e shows that the content of Fe (24.77%) and Mn (7.59%) elements decreased, but the content of Al

(1.16%) and Si (2.98%) increased. This is due to the presence of Al and Si content in the zeolite. Other elements present in the MnFe_2O_4 – zeolite adsorbent are Na, Mg, Cl, K, Ca, Ti, and V. The elements Na, K, and Ca are cations from zeolite, while the presence of elements Mg, and Ti are predicted to appear from sand that was used, while Cl probably appears from the use of the HCl solvent during the synthesis process. Element V is thought to have originated from the iron sand milling process which experienced abrasion in the jar mill or ball mill.

The results of the XRD measurements of the MnFe_2O_4 and MnFe_2O_4 – zeolite samples are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The pattern of diffraction peaks in MnFe_2O_4 and MnFe_2O_4 – zeolite samples

Figure 2 shows the XRD spectra for MnFe_2O_4 and MnFe_2O_4 – zeolite. It can be seen that MnFe_2O_4 adsorbent has several diffraction peaks with different intensities. The highest diffraction peak and several other peaks were identified phases at values 2θ of 35.57° , 46.82° , 56.76° and 62.13° with hkl planes (311), (331), (511), and (440) which were matched with JCPDS data No. 73-1964 [24]. At 2θ values of 27.40° and 39.80° TiO_2 compounds were identified, while at 2θ values of 12.22° and 16.39° SiO_2 compounds were identified. The formation of TiO_2 (from iron sand) and SiO_2 (from zeolite) can be seen from the presence of Ti, Si, and O elements in the sample as shown in the EDX analysis. Furthermore, in the XRD diffraction pattern of the MnFe_2O_4 – zeolite adsorbent, several peaks were also observed at 2θ values, they are at 12.74° , 16.37° , 20.86° , 26.57° , 35.61° , 39.46° , 47.00° , 56.88° , and 62.00° . In the analysis results, new phases appear at values of 2θ 12.74° , 16.37° , 20.86° , and 26.57° which were analyzed zeolite compounds (Hydrous sodium aluminum silicate) that were matched with JCPDS data No. 00-019-1180[25]. Analcime zeolite has the smallest pores and exhibits a compact structure. Compared to other zeolites with ideal unit cells $\text{Na}_{16}[(\text{AlO}_2)_{16}(\text{SiO}_2)_{32}]\cdot 16\text{H}_2\text{O}$ [26].

Furthermore, Figure 3 shows the hysteresis curve obtained from the VSM measurement for the MnFe_2O_4 and MnFe_2O_4 – zeolite samples.

Figure 3: Hysteresis curves of adsorbents for MnFe_2O_4 , and MnFe_2O_4 – zeolite

It is seen that from the shape of the hysteresis curve of the MnFe_2O_4 and MnFe_2O_4 – zeolite compounds that are shown in Fig. 3, both materials are ferrimagnetic and classified as soft-magnetic[27]. The MnFe_2O_4 adsorbent has a saturation magnetization value (M_s) of 1.03 emu/g, remanence magnetization (M_r) of 0.05 emu/g, and a coercivity value (H_c) of 302.12 Oe. Meanwhile, the adsorbent MnFe_2O_4 – zeolite has a M_s value of 1.02 emu/g, a M_r value of 0.06 emu/g, and an H_c value of 406.04 Oe. Based on these results, the small decrease in the M_s value for the MnFe_2O_4 – zeolite adsorbents is due to the zeolite being a non-magnetic material [28]. The low values of M_s , M_r , and H_c for both MnFe_2O_4 and MnFe_2O_4 – zeolite are predicted due to the presence of gangue or impurities as can be seen in the EDX and XRD results[29].

The adsorption-desorption isotherms of N_2 from MnFe_2O_4 and MnFe_2O_4 – zeolite samples results that are obtained from the BET measurement are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: adsorption-desorption isotherms of N_2 from adsorbents a) MnFe_2O_4 , and b) MnFe_2O_4 – zeolite

The N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms of the two adsorbents including the type V isotherm with the H₂ hysteresis loop between the adsorption and desorption curves at higher relative pressures, which shows a mesoporous surface with a complex pore structure interconnected with different sizes [30][31]. The mesoporous surface is evidenced by the pore size of the MnFe₂O₄ and MnFe₂O₄ – zeolite adsorbents, which are 2.63 nm and 2.70 nm. Differences in the shape and size of pores are caused by non-uniform particle size and shape, as shown by the SEM analysis. Calculation of the specific surface area of MnFe₂O₄ – zeolite (222.91 m²/g) is much larger than that of MnFe₂O₄ (193.03 m²/g), besides that the pore volume of MnFe₂O₄ – zeolite (0.30 cm³/g) is larger than that of the MnFe₂O₄ adsorbent (0.25 cm³/g). This is clearly due to zeolite being a material that has a high specific surface area and high porosity [32].

Adsorption of Pb and Cu

The Adsorption capacity of Pb and Cu ions by MnFe₂O₄ and MnFe₂O₄ – Zeolite adsorbents are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: The adsorption capacity of Pb and Cu ions by MnFe₂O₄ and MnFe₂O₄ – Zeolite adsorbents

Dose (mg)	pH	Contact Time (minute)	MnFe ₂ O ₄						MnFe ₂ O ₄ – Zeolite					
			Concentration (mg/L)				Adsorption Capacity (mg/g)		Concentration (mg/L)				Adsorption Capacity (mg/g)	
			Pb		Cu		Pb	Cu	Pb		Cu		Pb	Cu
			C _i	C _e	C _i	C _e			C _i	C _e	C _i	C _e		
50	5	60	8	0,276	8	0,061	2,57	2,44	8	0,248	8	0,037	2,58	2,65
100	5	60	8	0,273	8	0,064	3,86	3,97	8	0,261	8	0,040	3,88	3,98
150	5	60	8	0,282	8	0,069	7,72	7,94	8	0,263	8	0,047	7,74	7,96

The adsorption capacity and removal efficiency are obtained using [30]:

$$q = \frac{C_i - C_e}{w} \quad (1)$$

$$R = \frac{C_i - C_e}{C_i} 100\% \quad (2)$$

with: q = Adsorption capacity (mg/L), C_i = initial concentration (mg/L) C_e = Final concentration (mg/L), W = mass of magnetic powder (grams), R = Removal Efficiency (%).

As can be seen from Table 1 for MnFe₂O₄ the optimum adsorption capacity values were obtained at a dose of 50 mg/L for both Pb (7.72 mg/g) and Cu (7.94 mg/g) respectively. For MnFe₂O₄ – Zeolite also found the optimum adsorption capacity value at a dose of 50 mg/L for Pb (7.74 mg/g) and Cu (7.96 mg/g). The adsorption capacity decreased by increasing the dose in both adsorbents. This is predicted due to all the active sites are completely exposed at lower doses, whereas only a small proportion of active sites are exposed at higher doses. Thus, higher adsorbent doses can cause aggregation, which decreases the total surface area of the adsorbent and causes a decrease in adsorption [33]. Another possibility could be caused by the unsaturation of adsorption sites through adsorption reactions [34].

The optimum adsorption capacity value obtained for MnFe_2O_4 – zeolite adsorbent is slightly larger compared to the MnFe_2O_4 adsorbent for both Pb and Cu. This is due to the addition of zeolite to the adsorbent which increases the surface area, pore volume, and pore size thereby increasing the number of active sites on the surface which can increase the adsorption capacity [21].

The Removal Efficiency of Pb(II) and Cu(II) metal ions for MnFe_2O_4 and MnFe_2O_4 -Zeolite adsorbents at pH=5, T=25C, t= 60 minutes, $C_i = 8\text{mg/L}$ is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: The Removal Efficiency of Pb(II) and Cu(II) metal ions for MnFe_2O_4 dan MnFe_2O_4 -Zeolite adsorbents

From Figure 5, It can be seen that the removal efficiency of Cu(II) ions using both MnFe_2O_4 and MnFe_2O_4 -Zeolite adsorbents is higher than the removal efficiency of Pb(II) ions. This is due to the smaller radius of Cu(II) ions (0.72 \AA) compared to Pb(II) (1.29 \AA) so that Cu(II) metal ions can easily occupy the adsorption active sites on the adsorbent surface [31][32]. The removal efficiency value is also increased when the adsorbent dose increases from 50, 100, and 150 mg/L. By increasing the adsorbent dose, the number of active sites is also increased. Then particle aggregation will occur, which makes the adsorption efficiency of Pb and Cu increase.

The removal efficiency is also influenced by the use of adsorbent pH, where if the pH used is more than 6, Pb(II) ions will precipitate in the form of hydroxide ($\text{Pb}(\text{OH})_2$) which will reduce the concentration of Pb ions in the solution and then decrease the removal efficiency [1]. The presence of hydron ions (H^+) from the deprotonation of hydroxyl groups in water also affects the removal efficiency, where H^+ ions will compete with Pb(II) and Cu(II) ions to occupy active sites on the adsorbent [33].

The removal efficiency of Pb and Cu ions using MnFe₂O₄ - zeolite is higher than MnFe₂O₄ adsorbent, is also due to the addition of zeolite increases the surface area, thus increasing the number of adsorption active sites on the adsorbent surface [32], and also with the presence of Na⁺ cations from zeolite analcime can be exchanged with Pb²⁺ (1.29Å) or Cu²⁺ (0.72Å) cations [34][35]. Where the radius of Na ions is 1.02Å so, the addition of zeolite increases the surface area and increases the number of active adsorption sites on the surface of the adsorbent thereby increasing the adsorption capacity.

In Table 2 is given the comparison of adsorption capacity with various adsorbents for Pb(II), and Cu(II)

Table: 2

No	Sample	Adsorption capacities (mg g ⁻¹)		ref
		Pb	Cu	
1.	chitosan/graphene oxide composites	76.9	-	[35]
2.	GO	328	-	[36]
3.	EDTA-GO	479	-	[36]
4.	EDTA-RGO	204	-	[36]
5.	amino-functionalized carbon nanotubes	58.3	-	[37]
6.	MnFe ₂ O ₄ nanoparticles	488	-	[38]
7.	GO-MnFe ₂ O ₄ nanohybrids	673	-	[38]
8.	Fe ₃ O ₄ /Cu-MOFs	219.00	-	[39]
9.	ZnO/MMT	88.50	54.06	[40]
10.	CG	16.95	6.64	[41]
11.	CG-0.5GEC	16.95	7.91	[41]
12.	CG-1.0GEC	17.01	7.54	[41]
13.	CG-2.0GEC	17.70	8.64	[41]
14.	CMS@CS	-	63.7	[42]
15.	CMS@CS-F	-	66.7	[42]
16.	PANI@APTS-Fe ₃ O ₄ /ATP-0.7 (288K)	265.25	180.18	[43]
17.	PANI@APTS-Fe ₃ O ₄ /ATP-0.7 (298K)	270.27	189.03	[43]
18.	PANI@APTS-Fe ₃ O ₄ /ATP-0.7 (308K)	273.22	198.80	[43]
19.	EDTA-mGO (298K)	481.2	246.1	[44]
20.	EDTA-mGO (308K)	548.1	289.4	[44]
21.	EDTA-mGO (318K)	508.4	301.2	[44]
22.	chitosan-pyromellitic dianhydride	-	66.7432	[45]
23.	CFZ10-68	109.890	57.803	[46]
24.	ZRef - FAU	103.093	57.803	[46]
25.	Oxidized MWCNT/SDBS	66.95	-	[47]
26.	Oxidized MWCNT	17.5	-	[48]
27.	Activated carbon/zeolite	549.11	-	[49]
28.	MnFe ₂ O ₄	7,72	7,94	This work
29.	MnFe ₂ O ₄ – Zeolite	7,74	7,96	This work

As can be seen from Table 2 the adsorption capacity of Pb and Cu by several researchers using different samples. For example, in sample CG, batch mode adsorption studies of Cu(II), Ni(II), Pb(II), and Co(II) were conducted at 25°C using 200 ml of metal ion solutions with concentrations ranging from 10-50 mg/L and 400 mg of adsorbent with an adsorption capacity of 16.95 mg/g for Pb metal and 6.64 mg/g for Cu metal [41]. Compared to the results of our research which was also conducted at 25°C using 1L water solution has a

fairly good adsorption capacity for MnFe_2O_4 adsorbent of 7.72 mg/g for Pb metal and 7.94 mg/g for Cu metal. While MnFe_2O_4 -Zeolite adsorbent has an absorption capacity of 7,74 mg/g for Pb metal and 7,96 mg/g for Cu metal. The amount of both adsorbents was 150 mg and the initial concentration of Pb and Cu metal was 8 mg/L as seen in Table 1. We didn't do the variation concentration in this work due to the limitations of samples of Pb and Cu Metals.

CONCLUSION

In this study, MnFe_2O_4 and MnFe_2O_4 – Zeolite were successfully synthesized from sand and zeolite using the Co-precipitation method for the use as adsorbents for the adsorption of Pb(II) and Cu(II) ions from aqueous media. The results of the SEM-EDX analysis showed that the MnFe_2O_4 and MnFe_2O_4 – zeolite particles had non-uniform particle sizes with some impurities present. XRD analysis confirmed the presence of impurities with the appearance of TiO_2 and SiO_2 peaks. Both adsorbents are ferrimagnetic and show soft magnet behavior with a coercivity value of MnFe_2O_4 – zeolite is larger than MnFe_2O_4 . The BET analysis also showed that the surface area, pore volume, and pore size of the MnFe_2O_4 -zeolite adsorbent are larger than the MnFe_2O_4 adsorbents. From the adsorption test with the influence of the adsorbent dose, there was an increase in the percentage of optimum adsorption on Pb and Cu by using the MnFe_2O_4 - zeolite adsorbent. From this study, it is found that MnFe_2O_4 – zeolite is a very effective adsorbent in removing the Cu and Pb ions from the water solution.

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